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SPECIFICATION OF INPUT TO STEP 2/3
AND THE DOUBLE STAR ANALYSIS FROM DSRI

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document is a draft specification of the main data types to be sent from DSRI (output from the Great-Circle Reduction) to LO (input to Step 2/3 and the Double Star Analysis). The formats are modelled on those described in the document 'Specification of Input to the Great-Circle Reduction Programs' (Issue 2) by C Petersen (henceforth referred to as 'SIGCR'). The same general rules apply concerning the physical format, the organization of files, blocks, records, words, and bytes, storage of numerical values as non-negative integers, and the general file and block format (Sections 1 to 3 in SIGCR).

Two data types are described here:

'EABS' = estimated abscissae (one file per Great-Circle Reduction). This is the main input to Step 2/3;

'IATT' = instrument parameters and attitude (one file per GCR). This is input to the Double Star Analysis.

Because the abscissae, attitude, and instrument parameters generated by the same GCR are at this point separated from each other, we propose a unique identifier IDSET for the results of a particular GCR. IDSET is simply a sequential numbering of the GCR processes, so that reprocessing of the same input data would produce a different IDSET. Each GCR may produce at least two fundamentally different sets of output data, namely with and without dynamical smoothing. We propose to distinguish these results already by means of the IDSET numbering, in the following way. The results of the geometrical GCR's are numbered IDSET = 1, 2, 3, etc. A smoothed GCR is always based on a particular geometrical solution, say with identification number IDSETG. The different smoothed results based on this geometrical solution are then given identification numbers IDSET = IDSETG + 1e5, IDSETG + 2e5, etc. This permits a maximum of 99,999 geometrical solutions, each having a maximum of 21,474 smoothed versions (since IDSET must be .LT. 2**31).

2. FILE LABEL AND BLOCK HEADER RECORDS

The format of the File Label Record is described in SIGCR, Section 3.2, with 'EABS' or 'IATT' inserted as data type identifier (word 2).

The Block Header Record is described in SIGCR, Section 3.4.

3. ESTIMATED ABCISSA FILE FORMAT (data type 'EABS')

Each file contains results from one Great-Circle Reduction (GCR) to be used in Step 2/3, namely the definition of the set (time interval, RGC pole), the estimated abscissae and their standard errors. The abscissa records must be stored in order of increasing object identification number in the file. Results for solar system objects (asteroids and satellites) are not included (these will require a slightly different output format and should be directed to a different process).

3.1. File header record

The header record contains a reference epoch for all the abscissae in the file, the equatorial coordinates (equinox J2000) of the RGC pole, the approximate set interval, and the set identification number.

----- ESTIMATED ABCISSA FILE HEADER RECORD -----

Name	Off	Len	Description
LHEADR	0	4	= 13 Number of words in this header record
IDVERS	4	4	= 1 Version number of this file format
LRECFL	8	4	= 4 Number of words in an abscissa record
	12	4	= 0 Indicates a fixed length record
NRECFL	16	4	Number of abscissa records in the file
EPOCHR	20	4	Set reference epoch in seconds since J1988.0
ALPHAR	24	4	Right Ascension A [rad] of RGC pole stored as: int(A*2**24) where A is in the range 0 to 2*pi
	28	4	Remaining part RA of R.A. stored as: nint(RA*2**24) where RA = A*2**24-int(A*2**24)
DELTAR	32	4	Declination D [rad] of RGC pole stored as: int(D*2**24) where D is in the range 0 to 2*pi
	36	4	Remaining part RD of Dec. stored as: nint(RD*2**24) where RD = D*2**24-int(D*2**24)
FMTBEG	40	4	Integer part of the mid-time of the first frame used in the GCR, in seconds since J1988.0
FMTEND	44	4	Integer part of the mid-time of the last frame used in the GCR, in seconds since J1988.0
IDSET	48	4	Set identification number (see Introduction)

3.2. Estimated abscissa records

Each record contains, for a given object, the estimated abscissa and its estimated standard error. The records must be in order of increasing object identification number.

 ESTIMATED ABSCISSA RECORD

Name	Off	Len	Description
IDSTAR	0	4	Object identification number
EABSC	4	4	Estimated abscissa A [rad] stored as: int(A*2**24) where A is in the range 0 to 2*pi
	8	4	Remaining part RA of the abscissa stored as: nint(RA*2**24) where RA = A*2**24-int(A*2**24)
SDABSC	12	4	Estimated standard error S of the abscissa [rad] stored as: nint(1e11*S); 0 < S < 0.02

4. INSTRUMENT AND ATTITUDE DATA FILE FORMAT (data type 'IATT')

Each file contains results from one Great-Circle Reduction (GCR) to be used in the Double Star Analysis, namely the definition of the set (time interval), the estimated instrument parameters with standard errors, and the frame-by-frame attitude angles (of which the spin phase angle SPHASE has been improved by the GCR). The attitude records must be stored in order of increasing frame mid-time.

 4.1. File header record

The header record contains the approximate mid-times of the first and last frame used in the GCR, and the set identification number.

 INSTRUMENT AND ATTITUDE DATA FILE HEADER RECORD

Name	Off	Len	Description
LHEADR	0	4	= 8 Number of words in this header record
IDVERS	4	4	= 1 Version number of this file format
LRECFL	8	4	= 8 Number of words in an attitude record
	12	4	= 0 Indicates a fixed length record
NRECFL	16	4	Number of attitude records in the file
FMTBEG	20	4	Integer part of the mid-time of the first frame used in the GCR, in seconds since J1988.0
FMTEND	24	4	Integer part of the mid-time of the last frame used in the GCR, in seconds since J1988.0
IDSET	28	4	Set identification number (see Introduction)

4.2. Instrument parameters record

After the file header record follow the instrument parameters. This contains a header record specifying the number of instrument parameters and certain reference values, followed by one record per instrument parameter. The list must be complete in the sense that it contains all the parameters used for computing the Large-Scale Distortion in the GCR, even if they are not estimated by the GCR (they may be taken from some other set or special calibrations). Instrument parameters not estimated by the GCR are here distinguished by setting their standard error = 0.

The units for the instrument parameters are as proposed in 'A Format For Comparison of Great-Circle Reduction Results' by C Petersen (1987 Feb 3). They are designated by a non-negative integer IXYFCT defined as:

$$\text{IXYFCT} = 10000 \cdot \text{IX} + 1000 \cdot \text{IY} + 100 \cdot \text{IF} + 10 \cdot \text{IC} + \text{IT}$$

where IX, IY, IF, IC, and IT are the (non-negative) powers of the field coordinates (x, y; or w, z in the usual NDAC notation), the field index (f = 1 for preceding, -1 for following field), centred colour index c = (B-V) - 0.5, and centred time t = (T - (FMTBEG+FMTEND)/2)/43200. Thus, any basis function for the Large-Scale Distortion is of the form:

$$\text{func}(\text{IXYFCT}) = x^{**\text{IX}} * y^{**\text{IY}} * f^{**\text{IF}} * c^{**\text{IC}} * t^{**\text{IT}}$$

and the instrument parameter p(IXYFCT) is the coefficient of this function. The complete expression for the field-to-grid transformation is

$$G = \text{SCALE} * x + \text{SUM} \{ p(\text{IXYFCT}) * \text{func}(\text{IXYFCT}) \}$$

where the sum is taken over the parameters listed. SCALE is a reference value for the scale, relative to which the parameter IXYFCT = 10000 is defined. Also the parameter IXYFCT = 00100 (a.k.a. h00) is defined relative to some reference value for the basic angle (BANGLE). To avoid any ambiguity as to the choice of these reference values, they are given at the beginning of the record. (Note: SCALE is by convention a negative number, approximately SCALE = -170731.7073 slits/rad. However, it is stored in this record as a positive integer, see below. BANGLE is always positive.) The blocksize (2048 words) allows a maximum of 676 instrument parameters.

INSTRUMENT PARAMETERS RECORD

Name	Off	Len	Description
=====			
(header record:)			
	0	4	= 4 Number of words in this header record
NPARAM	4	4	Number of instrument parameters
SCALE	8	4	Reference value for the scale [slits/rad] stored as: nint(-1e4*SCALE)
BANGLE	12	4	Reference value for the basic angle [rad] stored as: nint(1e11*(BANGLE - 1))

(first instrument parameters record:)

IXYFCT	16	4	Designation of the first instrument parameter
PARAM	20	4	First parameter value [mas, mas/hfov, mas/mag, mas/(12 h), etc] stored as: $\text{nint}(1e3*PARAM)+1e8$
SDPAR	24	4	Standard error of the first parameter [same unit as PARAM] stored as: $\text{nint}(1e3*SDPAR)+1e8$

(second instrument parameters record:)

IXYFCT	28	4	Designation for the second instrument parameter
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.

(there are NPARAM instrument parameters records)

4.3. Attitude records

Each record contains the heliotropic attitude angles for a given frame mid-time. The first two angles (RANGLE and RPHASE), which specify the estimated position of the rotation (z) axis, are normally taken directly from the OGAR attitude determined at RGO, while the third angle (SPHASE) has been improved by the GCR process. However, since the determination of SPHASE depends on the assumed values for RANGLE and RPHASE, it is necessary (and convenient) to give all three angles here. The records must be in chronological order (increasing frame mid-times), but there may be gaps (jet firings, occultations, empty frames).

ATTITUDE RECORD

Name	Off	Len	Description
FMTIME	0	4	Frame mid-time in seconds since J1988.0
	4	4	Micro-seconds part of the frame mid-time
RANGLE	8	4	Estimated revolving angle A [rad] stored as: $\text{int}(A*2**24)$ where A is in the range 0 to $2*\pi$
	12	4	Remaining part RA of the rev. angle stored as: $\text{nint}(RA*2**24)$ where $RA = A*2**24 - \text{int}(A*2**24)$
RPHASE	16	4	Estimated revolving phase P [rad] stored as: $\text{int}(P*2**24)$ where P is in the range 0 to $2*\pi$
	20	4	Remaining part RP of the rev. phase stored as: $\text{nint}(RP*2**24)$ where $RP = P*2**24 - \text{int}(P*2**24)$
SPHASE	24	4	Estimated spin phase S [rad] stored as: $\text{int}(S*2**24)$ where S is in the range 0 to $2*\pi$
	28	4	Remaining part RS of the spin phase stored as: $\text{nint}(RS*2**24)$ where $RS = S*2**24 - \text{int}(S*2**24)$